

Illegal Oil Bunkering and National Security: An Assessment of the Niger Delta Region

Oba Preye Inimiesi¹ & Ebiendu Yoroki²

¹Department of Public Administration, ²Department of Political Science,
Faculty of Social and Management Sciences, University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Bayelsa State,
Nigeria. ¹preye.oba@uat.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14921805>

Abstract

This study assessed the impact of illegal oil bunkering on national security in the Niger Delta region. Using the mixed methods approach, this study aims to not only consider the effects of illegal oil bunkering on national security but to equally examine the factors contributing to violent confrontations associated with illegal oil bunkering, including the involvement of security forces and rival factions in the Niger Delta region. A mixed-method approach was adopted to achieve the objectives of the study, using both quantitative and qualitative techniques for data gathering and analysis. The sample size for the study was 400. Data gathering for this study was largely through an online questionnaire survey and telephone-based Key Persons Interview (KPI). In the course of the study, 312 respondents filled out the online survey, and 18 interview participants were engaged. The related data from the online questionnaire survey were collated and analysed, using percentages and frequencies reflected through a chart, while the interview information was transcribed and analysed thematically. The results from the data analysis revealed, among others, that the pervasive impact of illegal oil bunkering on human and national security underscores a complex web of challenges. The study recommends that the Nigerian government, along with other African nations in the Gulf of Guinea, should supply updated satellite equipment so that all cargo and crude oil boats operating in the sub-region can be seen and tracked. This will help to monitor and enforce the appropriate prosecution of oil ships and vessels engaged in unlawful bunkering on the high seas.

Keywords: *Illegal, oil-bunkering, national security, Niger Delta.*

Introduction

The stability and survival of nations are intricately intertwined with the availability and safeguarding of critical resources, with oil reigning supreme among them. Oil's pervasive influence extends far beyond mere economic realms, permeating into the very fabric of national security and development strategies worldwide. Oil is a strategically important resource that has enormous political and economic implications for many nations (Gilpin, 2018). It not only drives economic expansion but also gives governments a source of income and is essential in determining both national and global policy (Campbell, 2019). The hunt for oil has historically propelled countries to extreme measures, influencing diplomatic moves, wars, and geopolitical alliances. Given its vital role in promoting economic growth, earning government money, and

affecting both domestic and foreign politics, its status as a strategic resource is indisputable. Rich oil-producing nations have enormous sway over the world stage; they frequently use their riches of natural resources to establish domination or gain favourable positions in geopolitical spheres. Oil's importance goes beyond its status as a commodity; in a globe growing more interconnected by the day, countries trying to preserve their stability and existence continue to place a high priority on achieving energy security.

Nigeria, like many other nations, grapples with the profound economic and political implications of its oil wealth. The nation's future is inextricably linked to the extraction of crude oil, which drives the Nigerian economy (Nkechi, 2023). Endowed with substantial reserves, oil plays a pivotal role in shaping Nigeria's national identity, economic trajectory, and political landscape. Nigeria's centre for natural gas and crude oil production is the Niger Delta, which is home to several subsurface and surface product pipeline networks. Oil drilling in the Niger Delta started in the early 20th century, driven by colonial interests (Ekweozor, 2015), and it had a significant impact on the socioeconomic growth of Nigeria. With more than 600 oil fields, 5,284 oil wells, 10 oil and gas export terminals, 275 flow stations, 10 gas plants, massive liquefied natural gas, and the starting point of more than 700 kilometres of pipelines throughout the nation, the Niger Delta produces more than 80% of Nigeria's oil (Boris & Job, 2015). Oil and gas resources from the region provide 80 per cent of government revenue, 95 per cent of foreign exchange earnings and 96 per cent of export revenues (Ibora, 2009). The Niger Delta is one of the world's largest wetlands, one of the 20 major deltas in the world and Africa's largest delta and perhaps, the richest in the world in terms of oil and gas reserves, covering some 70 000 km² (Badmus, 2010; Fagbadebo and Akinola, 2010). Thus, Wilson (2012) aptly states that the increase in crude oil production directly affects the revenue base and development programs of the Nigerian state and, by extension, national security. Crude oil is, as previously stated, the mainstay of Nigeria's economy.

Paradoxically, the region represents one of the worst cases of severe poverty and underdevelopment while having such a vast base of natural resources. There has been very little in the way of infrastructure development; poverty and unemployment are at 80% and 85%, respectively (Boris & Job, 2015). There is extremely little access to essential social facilities. All development metrics or indicators show that the region is less developed than the national average (Ibaba, 2005; Ejovi, Ebie, & Akpokighe, 2014). Conflicts between the Niger Delta people, the oil companies, and the federal government have arisen as a result of the region's oil exploration and extraction operations, which have damaged the people's means of

subsistence. These confrontations culminated in the emergence of several groups advocating for the improvement of the Niger Delta's environmental conditions (Ikelegbe, 2010). However, as a result of the appropriate authorities for the area paying insufficient attention, there was an armed war marked by kidnapping, oil theft, bombing of oil installations, and illegal oil bunkering (Obi, 2010).

Both national security and sustainable development are seriously threatened by illegal bunkering, which includes illicit operations related to the excavation, theft, and smuggling of crude oil (Adams, 2017). According to international organisations, this illegal activity—which is typified by oil theft, pipeline sabotage, and smuggling—not only threatens the environment and the economy in several African nations, but it also poses security risks, particularly to host communities (Okoh, 2018; Smith, 2019; Jones, 2020). Both governments and oil firms suffer significant income losses as a result of this approach. According to statistics, oil bunkering causes Nigeria to lose over 400,000 barrels of oil per day, or US\$1.7 billion, each month (Dalby, 2014). Many of the operators and oil thieves who are involved in bunkering and refining on a direct or indirect basis profit from this multibillion-dollar industry. They have established social welfare programmes in the area to get social licenses from the host communities. This loss has a significant negative effect on national budgets and prevents expenditures in healthcare, education, and infrastructure (White, 2018). Conflicts over resources are also frequently caused by illegal oil bunkering, which deteriorates and contaminates land and water supplies that are vital to livelihoods. More importantly, poverty and unemployment are fueling grounds for criminal activity, and they are caused by the diversion of national resources from legal channels. Illegal bunkering activities worsen the security situation since they sometimes include armed organisations that engage in violent conflicts with opposing factions or security forces, putting the lives of bystanders in jeopardy. The practice has grown to be a significant source of income for criminal organisations, which has raised the risk of bloodshed, social discontent, and instability.

The activity has heightened various forms of violence, including kidnappings, attacks on oil installations, and clashes between rival gangs, all of which have contributed to the insecurity in the region. The situation in the Niger Delta has prompted the government to introduce various measures to curb illegal bunkering, including the establishment of the Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency (NIMASA) to regulate and enforce maritime activities, the establishment of the Joint Task Force (JTF), the Niger Delta Development Commission (NDDC), the enactment of laws such as the Oil Pipeline Act and the Oil Theft

and Pipeline Vandalism Act, the creation of the Ministry of Niger Delta Affairs, and the implementation of the Presidential Amnesty Programme (PAP) to address the underlying causes of militancy and illegal bunkering, yet constant vandalisation of pipelines and other oil facilities across the country as well as the transaction in stolen oil by these criminals with international connection have continued to be a problem for both the government and citizens alike (Mernyi, 2014). These efforts demonstrate the government's commitment to addressing the issue of illegal oil bunkering and promoting security in the Niger Delta region. It is on this foundation that this study seeks to interrogate the nexus between the menace of illegal oil bunkering and national security to provide an actionable blueprint out of it. Based on this, the objectives of the study are to assess the impact of illegal oil bunkering on national security in the region and examine the factors contributing to violent confrontations associated with illegal oil bunkering, including the involvement of security forces and rival factions.

Literature Review

Illegal bunkering in the Niger Delta

The process of syphoning crude oil from pipelines, moving it to improvised refineries, and distilling it into products like kerosene, diesel, and petrol is known as illegal bunkering. Oil bunkering continues to be a significant problem for Nigeria, affecting people's lives, the environment, and the country's economy despite the uproar over deaths (Abdulahi, 2022; Ediri, 2022). In the Niger Delta, oil bunkering is a common and surprisingly transparent illegal activity. It is widespread in several locations, including Bayelsa, Port Harcourt, Warri, Okrika, Bonny, Akassa, and Soku. Major loading sites for oil exports to the global market are located in this region. Cawthorne Channel and Jones Creek are two other important locations. According to statistics, oil bunkering causes Nigeria to lose over 400,000 barrels of oil per day, or US\$1.7 billion, each month (Dalby, 2014). Another study from the local media site Dataphyt claims that in 2020, theft and sabotage of crude oil cost the nation at least \$1.6 billion and over 39 million barrels. According to the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission, Nigeria lost more than 115,000 barrels of crude oil during January and February 2022, or \$3.27 billion.

Illegal oil bunkering has made oil spillages and explosions a common occurrence in the Niger Delta region using a variety of techniques, amounts, and procedures (Campbell, 2015). The most common ways to steal crude oil are to tap it at the location where it has been pierced for

trade and commercial reasons or to break the pipeline that transports the commodity from one place to another (Adedoyin, 2016; Adishi & Hunga, 2017). Previous studies (Adishi & Hunga, 2017; Katsouris & Sayne, 2013) have shown that oil theft and illicit bunkering manifest in the following ways:

- a) The small-scale oil theft for resale in the local market.
- b) Direct tapping into pipeline joints with a horsehead from the wellhead through the practical removal of the Christmas tree and joints.
- c) Unlicensed and forged bills of lading for resale of excess lifting of crude oil.
- d) The destruction of the company pipeline with explosives for disruption of oil supply to loading stations.

To cause havoc, community members in the first category typically operate under the cover of violence in the Niger Delta region. In contrast, the second category uses more advanced technology to extract crude and sell it in barges into the seashore for transportation into vessels in exchange for cash and weapons that incite violence. However, the third method results from the theft and corruption of authorities tasked with granting licenses to purchasers, who then resell the goods on the black market using falsified bills of lading to benefit themselves (Boris, 2015). The last one, according to Adishi and Hunga (2017), combines political influence with categories one and two. The majority of oil spills, environmental degradation, and pollution are caused by the last category, which also targets oil installations and pipelines with bombs and blasts in an attempt to stop the supply and production of crude oil as payback for the government and major oil industry players' disregard for societal needs. Due to socioeconomic factors like poverty, unemployment, political marginalisation, and the promise of large financial gains, the phenomenon is fairly common in the region and varies depending on the location (Okafor, 2016; Dornelles, 2016; Shrestha, 2017). Kenneth (2021) provided evidence to support this point of view by stating that the absence of alternative economic options and the belief that oil money may be used to escape poverty have encouraged people to engage in illicit bunkering operations. Furthermore, the Nigerian government's historical marginalisation and neglect of the Niger Delta area have fueled resentment and given rise to illegal bunkering as a means of resistance and financial survival (Effiong, 2019). Governments and oil firms suffer huge financial losses as a result of the problem, which is made worse by weak law enforcement and corruption. Over the previous two years, the Niger Delta clean-up has cost USD 360 million, thanks to the efforts of Nigeria's national oil corporation and its joint venture partners (Bodo & Gimah, 2020). According to SPDC, sabotage against their facilities was the cause of 70% of all oil leaks during the previous five years (Campbell, 2015).

Illegal Oil Bunkering and National Security

Nigeria is one of the biggest oil producers in Africa. Thus, the effects of this illegal activity go well beyond just financial losses. According to international organisations, this illegal activity—which is characterised by oil theft, pipeline sabotage, and smuggling—not only threatens national security but also undermines economic and environmental sustainability in several African nations (Adams, 2017; Okoh, 2018). It is a dangerous force that threatens the foundation of the country's stability and security. It serves as a multifaceted catalyst for the numerous security issues besetting Nigeria.

The fundamental aspect of illegal oil bunkering is that it is a criminal enterprise run by syndicates that steal and trade crude oil and refined petroleum products for profit. These syndicates use a variety of sophisticated and frequently violent tactics, such as pipeline sabotage, illegal refining, and smuggling (Boris, 2015; Raimi, 2023). The substantial profits made from oil bunkering not only support these networks but also give them the ability to grow, corrupt officials, and continue a cycle of violence and impunity. What's more, diverting national revenue from legal channels leads to poverty and unemployment, both of which serve as havens for criminal activity. The practice has grown to be a significant source of income for criminal organisations, which has raised the risk of bloodshed, social discontent, and instability. Illegal bunkering activities worsen the security situation since they sometimes include armed organisations that engage in violent conflicts with opposing factions or security forces, putting the lives of bystanders in jeopardy. The practice has grown to be a significant source of income for criminal organisations, which has raised the risk of bloodshed, social discontent, and instability.

Under the cover of illicit oil operations, terrorism, insurgency, and organised crime flourish thanks to the enormous resources available to criminal syndicates. Profits from oil theft are used by terrorist organisations like Boko Haram and militants in the Niger Delta to fund their activities, enlist new soldiers, and continue acts of violence (Gubak & Bulus, 2018; Allen, 2024). In addition to undermining official authority, the rise of armed organisations exacerbates societal tensions and fosters a culture of fear and insecurity. The region's level of insecurity has increased as a result of the activity, which has increased different types of crime, such as kidnappings, assaults on oil installations, and conflicts between competing gangs. In addition to its immediate security implications, oil bunkering erodes the foundations of governance and the rule of law in Nigeria. Corruption permeates various levels of government and law enforcement agencies, enabling collusion with criminal syndicates and perpetuating a culture of impunity. Raimi (2023) argues that the prevailing socio-economic conditions, characterised

by systemic corruption and limited economic opportunities, create a conducive environment for illegal oil bunkering to thrive. The inability of authorities to effectively combat oil bunkering not only undermines public trust in institutions but also hampers efforts to establish accountable and transparent governance structures.

Methodology

The study covered the Niger Delta region, and a mixed methods research design involving the use of quantitative and qualitative techniques was deployed. According to the NPC (2006), the area has a population of 31 million, two hundred and twenty-four thousand, five hundred and eighty-seven (31, 224,587), accounting for 25% of Nigeria's total population. The sample size of this study is 400 household heads drawn using the Taro Yamane statistical technique for the quantitative aspect of the research and 18 key persons interviewees for the qualitative aspect of the study. The multi-stage involving cluster, simple random, systematic random and purposive sampling techniques were opted for in this study. The study's primary data were gathered through a questionnaire, while secondary data was obtained from published sources. The descriptive-analytical technique was utilised to interpret the data in this study. The data were summarised using frequencies and central tendency metrics through the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS).

Results

Questionnaire Analysis

Objective 1: To assess the impact of illegal oil bunkering on national security in the Niger Delta region.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Out of 312 respondents, 147 agreed that illegal oil bunkering has significantly impacted human and national security. They highlighted that this illicit activity has destroyed traditional sources of livelihood, fueled the proliferation of armed groups, and caused widespread public health crises. Additionally, respondents noted that the pollution of the environment due to oil bunkering has led to the spread of diseases, exacerbating the health challenges faced by communities in the Niger Delta. This underscores the multifaceted threats posed by illegal oil bunkering, which extend beyond economic losses to encompass severe social and environmental consequences.

Objective 2: To examine the factors contributing to violent confrontations associated with illegal oil bunkering, including the involvement of security forces and rival factions.

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Figure 2 illustrates that among the aggregate respondents, 18% identified arms proliferation as a major factor contributing to violent confrontations in the region. A more substantial 37% attributed the issue to the lucrative economic incentives driving illegal oil bunkering. Additionally, 7% cited the lack of alternative opportunities as a contributing factor, while 10% linked the violence to environmental degradation. Another 14% associated the problem with the involvement of security forces and weak governance, highlighting the complex interplay of factors that fuel violence and insecurity in the Niger Delta.

Interview Analysis

Following the KPIs, two significant themes emerged that formed the sub-headings under which the results are discussed here. Below, the themes are discussed and supported with verbatim quotes from the interviewees where necessary.

Theme 1: Impact of illegal oil bunkering on security in the Niger Delta region

There was a consensus among the Key Person Interview (KPI) participants regarding the profound impact of illegal oil bunkering on security in the Niger Delta region. Almost all respondents agreed that illegal oil bunkering has significantly exacerbated insecurity in the region, contributing to a complex web of violence, environmental degradation, and economic instability. One participant summarised this sentiment, stating,

“Illegal bunkering has turned the Niger Delta into a battlefield. The security situation has deteriorated because everyone—militants, criminals, even some corrupt officials—is involved, and they all want a piece of the pie (Male KPI participant, aged 53).”

This observation highlights how the pursuit of illicit profits has not only intensified conflict among different groups but also undermined the rule of law, making the region increasingly ungovernable.

The participants also pointed out that the involvement of armed groups in illegal oil bunkering has led to the proliferation of weapons and the militarisation of local conflicts, further destabilising the region. One respondent noted,

“The money from bunkering is used to buy arms, which are then used to protect the operations or to fight rival groups. It’s a vicious cycle that keeps feeding itself (Male KPI participant, aged 47).”

This militarisation has had a ripple effect, with violence spilling over into local communities, exacerbating tensions, and creating an environment where fear and insecurity are pervasive. The easy access to weapons has emboldened criminal elements and militant groups, leading to more frequent and more violent confrontations, both within the illegal bunkering networks and between these groups and state security forces.

Furthermore, the environmental destruction caused by illegal oil bunkering has had a devastating impact on the livelihoods of local communities, compounding the security challenges in the Niger Delta. The widespread pollution of land and waterways has rendered

large areas uninhabitable and unsuitable for agriculture or fishing, driving more people into poverty and desperation. One participant expressed this concern, saying,

“The oil spills from bunkering have destroyed our farmlands and rivers. People can’t fish, they can’t farm, so they either join the bunkering or they starve. It’s a lose-lose situation (Male KPI participant, aged 42).”

This environmental degradation has not only contributed to the economic hardship faced by the local population. Still, it has also fueled further unrest as more individuals turn to illegal activities as a means of survival. The consensus among the KPI participants was clear: the security implications of illegal oil bunkering are far-reaching, affecting not just the immediate safety of individuals but also the long-term stability and development of the entire Niger Delta region.

Theme 2: Factors leading to violent confrontations associated with illegal oil bunkering

Concerning the factors contributing to violent confrontations linked to illegal oil bunkering, the Key Person Interview (KPI) participants expressed a range of perspectives, reflecting the complexity of the issue. Some participants highlighted the significant economic incentives associated with the activity, noting that the financial rewards from illegal oil bunkering are substantial enough to fuel intense competition and conflict among those involved. One participant remarked,

The probability of violent confrontations is very high due to the wealth generated from oil bunkering activities, with individuals driven by the desire to maximise profits and often prepared to pay the price for that achievement. This lucrative enterprise attracts various factions, each vying for control and willing to engage in violent clashes to secure their share of the profits. The substantial financial rewards serve as a powerful motivator, overshadowing the significant risks involved and perpetuating a cycle of violence as different groups compete fiercely to dominate the illegal oil bunkering operations (male, KPI participant, aged 42).

Another participant echoed this sentiment, emphasizing that

“The money in illegal oil bunkering is enormous, and when you have so much at stake, people will inevitably fight to protect their interests (Female KPI participant, aged 41).”

This view underscores the idea that the lucrative nature of oil bunkering creates a fertile ground for clashes of interest as various groups seek to secure their share of the profits, often leading to violent confrontations. Other KPI participants focused on the rivalry among factions vying for control over lucrative bunkering operations, which they identified as a key driver of

violence in the region. According to these respondents, the struggle for dominance among competing groups often escalates into armed conflicts, exacerbating the already volatile security situation in the Niger Delta. One respondent explained,

"Rival factions are constantly at each other's throats, trying to take control of the most profitable bunkering routes and operations. This competition naturally leads to violence (Male KPI participant, aged 47)."

Another participant added that:

"These groups are like gangs; they fight each other for control of the best routes and refineries. It's like a turf war, and it's bloody (Male KPI participant, aged 53)."

This factionalism not only leads to frequent and deadly clashes but also perpetuates a cycle of violence that is difficult to break. The constant struggle for control over illegal bunkering operations exacerbates existing tensions within the Niger Delta, contributing to the overall instability of the region. The proliferation of arms among these factions further intensifies the violence, as heavily armed groups are better equipped to engage in prolonged and destructive confrontations. This situation is made worse by the involvement of security forces, who are sometimes accused of complicity or corruption, further complicating efforts to restore order and curb illegal activities. Additionally, a segment of KPI participants pointed to socio-economic disenfranchisement and the lack of alternative livelihoods as fundamental factors driving individuals into illicit activities like oil bunkering, further complicating efforts to curb both violence and illegal practices. They argued that many people in the Niger Delta region resort to bunkering not out of choice but out of desperation, driven by poverty and the absence of viable economic opportunities. As one participant noted,

"When there's no work and no hope, people will do whatever it takes to feed their families, even if it means breaking the law (Female KPI participant, aged 44)."

This sentiment was echoed by another respondent, who added,

"When people feel they have nothing to lose, they are more likely to engage in dangerous and illegal activities, which only makes the situation more violent region (Male KPI participant, aged 53)."

This socio-economic desperation is compounded by the environmental degradation caused by oil spills and bunkering activities, which have destroyed traditional sources of livelihood such

as fishing and farming. The environmental destruction, in turn, exacerbates poverty and drives more individuals toward illegal bunkering as a means of survival, creating a vicious cycle. Moreover, the weak governance and frequent violation of the rule of law by the ruling class were also cited as contributing factors. As another participant observed,

“When the government is corrupt and doesn’t care about the people, it’s no surprise that the rule of law breaks down, and people take matters into their own hands (Male KPI participant, aged 47).”

This erosion of trust in government institutions and the law fosters an environment where illegal activities can thrive, further destabilizing the region. The interplay of economic, social, and political factors creates a complex and volatile situation in the Niger Delta, making it challenging to implement effective solutions to curb violence and illegal oil bunkering. These insights suggest that addressing the socio-economic root causes of illegal oil bunkering is crucial to reducing the violence associated with it, as providing alternative livelihoods and improving living conditions may help dissuade individuals from participating in such risky and illicit ventures.

Theme 3: Effective Strategies to combat illegal oil bunkering in the Niger Delta

The results from the KPIs revealed diverse strategies to combat illegal oil bunkering in the Niger Delta, including technological surveillance, military deployment, modular refineries, and engaging ex-militants. Respondents in the key person interview emphasized the critical need for deploying advanced surveillance technology to protect Nigeria's oil pipelines from illegal bunkering. Several respondents highlighted the limitations of current security measures and underscored the importance of leveraging modern technology to enhance monitoring and detection capabilities. As one respondent stated,

“Relying solely on physical patrols has proven inadequate in addressing the challenges of illegal oil bunkering. To enhance pipeline security, there is a pressing need to invest in advanced surveillance technologies such as drones, sensors, and satellite imagery. These tools would enable continuous monitoring and provide real-time data, allowing for quicker detection and response to breaches. (Male KPI participant, aged 42).”

Another interviewee echoed this sentiment, emphasizing that.

“Technology represents the future of pipeline security. By utilizing real-time data, we can swiftly detect and address any breaches in the pipeline system, ensuring a more effective and timely response. This approach not only enhances monitoring capabilities but also significantly reduces the risk of illegal activities, making it a crucial tool in safeguarding critical oil infrastructure (Female KPI participant, aged 44).”

The consensus among these respondents was that technology could provide a proactive approach to securing oil infrastructure, reducing the frequency and impact of illegal activities. In addition to advocating for technological solutions, some respondents in the interview stressed the importance of deploying more military personnel to the Niger Delta region. They argued that an increased military presence would serve as a deterrent to those involved in illegal bunkering. However, they also suggested that the establishment of modular refineries within the region could significantly reduce the incentives for such illicit activities. One respondent explained,

“If individuals are provided with legal avenues to refine and profit from oil, the appeal of engaging in illegal bunkering will significantly decrease. By establishing legitimate economic opportunities, such as modular refineries, communities can shift away from illicit activities. This approach not only curtails illegal bunkering but also promotes sustainable development and economic stability in the region (Male KPI participant, aged 53).”

Another added,

“Modular refineries have the potential to generate employment and bring economic benefits to local communities, thereby reducing the inclination toward illegal activities as a means of survival. By offering legitimate income opportunities, these refineries can help address the root causes of illegal bunkering, fostering economic growth and stability while promoting lawful livelihoods in the Niger Delta region (Male KPI participant, aged 47).”

This dual approach of enhancing security through military deployment and addressing the economic drivers of illegal bunkering through local refineries was seen as a comprehensive strategy to tackle the issue. Other respondents offered a more unconventional solution, suggesting that former militants be tasked with guarding the pipelines. These individuals, who are intimately familiar with the terrain and the tactics used by illegal bunkers, could be an effective force in protecting the region's oil infrastructure. One respondent argued,

“Who better to protect the pipelines than those who once participated in illegal activities? Their intimate knowledge of the operations and tactics involved in oil bunkering positions them uniquely to anticipate and prevent these crimes. By turning former militants into protectors, we can leverage their experience to enhance pipeline security and reduce illegal bunkering effectively (Male KPI participant, aged 42).”

Another respondent added,

“Engaging ex-militants in this way gives them a stake in the system. It transforms them from part of the problem to part of the solution infrastructure (Female KPI participant, aged 41).”

This perspective reflects a belief that involving former combatants in the security framework could not only reduce illegal bunkering but also help reintegrate these individuals into society

in a constructive manner. By offering them legitimate employment opportunities, the strategy aims to reduce the likelihood of their return to criminal activities and contribute to long-term peace and stability in the Niger Delta.

Discussion of Findings

The discussion of findings is conducted in alignment with the research objectives of this study, bringing to light several key insights. The first major finding, which aligns with Objective 1 and is illustrated in Figure 1, indicates that illegal oil bunkering has had a devastating impact on traditional sources of livelihood in the Niger Delta. This aligns with Abdulahi (2022), who reported that oil bunkering continues to be a significant problem for Nigeria, affecting people's lives, the environment, and the country's economy despite the uproar over deaths. In the same vein, the finding supports Jones (2020), who espoused that this illegal activity—which is typified by oil theft, pipeline sabotage, and smuggling—not only threatens the environment and the economy in several African nations but also poses security risks, particularly to host communities. This illicit activity has not only destroyed the economic foundations of many communities—particularly those reliant on farming and fishing—but has also fueled the proliferation of armed groups. The resulting violence has created a security crisis that is deeply intertwined with the economic and environmental instability of the region. Additionally, respondents highlighted that the environmental pollution caused by oil bunkering has led to widespread public health crises, with diseases proliferating as a direct consequence of contaminated water and soil. The KPIs further validated these findings, with a general consensus among participants that illegal oil bunkering has significantly exacerbated insecurity in the Niger Delta. Nearly all respondents agreed that the activity contributes to a complex web of violence, environmental degradation, and economic instability, making it a central issue in the region's ongoing security challenges. This convergence of opinions underscores the critical need for comprehensive strategies that address both the immediate and long-term impacts of illegal oil bunkering on the livelihoods and health of affected communities.

The second key finding, aligned with Objective 2 and illustrated in Figure 2, reveals that the persistence of illegal oil bunkering and associated violent confrontations in the Niger Delta is driven by several interconnected factors, including the lucrative economic incentives, arms proliferation, socio-economic disenfranchisement, environmental degradation, and the complicit or ineffective involvement of security forces, exacerbated by weak governance. This finding aligns with the Niger Delta Partnership Initiative (2022), which reported that the economic incentives, and high unemployment rates in the Niger Delta region drive individuals

to seek alternative income sources like illegal oil bunkering for financial gain, even though it is risky and illegal. Again, the KPIs supported these findings, with participants expressing that the combination of economic incentives (financial rewards), rivalry among factions, arms proliferation, and socio-economic challenges creates a volatile situation that perpetuates illegal oil bunkering and the violence associated with it. These insights emphasise the need for multi-faceted solutions that not only address the economic drivers of illegal bunkering but also strengthen governance and provide viable alternatives for those living in the Niger Delta.

Conclusion

The study emphasizes how crucial national security in the Niger Delta area and illicit oil bunkering connect. The results clearly show the variety of hazards that this illegal activity poses, from social instability and economic sabotage to environmental destruction. All parties involved—including governmental organizations, law enforcement organisations, local communities, and foreign allies—must work together to combat this threat. Effective measures to prevent illicit oil bunkering must be taken to safeguard natural resources, advance sustainable development, and improve both national and regional security. To lessen the negative effects of this widespread issue and promote a more safe and prosperous future for the Niger Delta and the country as a whole, proactive steps must be taken right away.

Recommendations

- i. The Nigerian government, in partnership with the oil multinationals, should set up modular refineries in the Niger Delta.
- ii. The Multinationals should be sincere in their corporate social responsibilities to the host communities.
- iii. The Nigerian government, along with oil multinational corporations, needs to set up sufficient surveillance systems in rural and interior regions where pipelines and other oil installations are located. These systems would monitor the actions of oil vandals and bunkers.
- iv. The Nigerian government, in tandem with other African nations in the Gulf of Guinea, needs to supply state-of-the-art satellite equipment to display and track all cargo and crude oil boats functioning in the subregion. This will help monitor and enforce the appropriate prosecution of oil ships and boats engaged in unlawful bunkering on the high seas.

- v. The Nigerian government should vigorously punish perpetrators of illegal bunkering activities in consonance with the rule of law (that is, processed through the Police, the court, and the correctional service) irrespective of their ranks and status in society so as to serve as a deterrent to others. To guarantee this, a unique law court should be set up for the prosecution of oil theft criminals, and all state security agencies participating in oil installation surveillance—not only the Nigeria Police Force—should be given the legal authority to prosecute such offenders.

References

- Abdulahi, T. (2022). *Illegal oil refining has cost Nigeria their lives and the environment for decades*. *Popular science*. <https://www.popsoci.com/environment/illegal-oil-refining-issues-nigeria/>
- Adams, P. (2017). The political economy of illegal oil bunkering in the Niger Delta. *Journal of African Political Studies*, 24(3), 45-62.
- Adedoyin, A. (2016). Pipeline Vandalism: Implications on Economy. Retrieved from <http://www.economicconfidential.com/2016/05/pipeline-vandalism-implications-economy/>
- Adishi, E., & Hunga, M.O. (2017). Oil Theft, Illegal Bunkering and Pipeline Vandalism: Its Impact on Nigeria Economy, 2015 – 2016. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*. 3(2), 47-65. <http://large.stanford.edu/courses/2020/ph240/bolodeoku2/docs/adishi-2017.pdf>
- Allen, F. (2024). Nigeria's Oil Wealth and International Relations Multilateral and Bilateral Lending and Decolonial Therapies: IFRI Papers. Available at https://www.ifri.org/sites/default/files/migrated_files/documents/atoms/files/ifri_allen_nigeria_oil_wealth_2024.pdf
- Boris, H. O. & Job, E. (2015). The irony of the amnesty programme: Incessant oil theft and illegal bunkering In the Niger Delta Region of Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 4(8), 09-18.
- Boris, O. H. (2015). Upsurge of oil theft and illegal bunkering in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria: Is there a way out? *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(3), 563-573. <https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2015.v6n3s2p563>
- Campbell, J. (2019). Oil and international politics: The impact of oil on national security. *International Relations Quarterly*, 41(2), 89-104.
- Campbell, J. (2015). *A primer on Nigeria's oil bunkering*. council on foreign relations. <https://www.cfr.org/blog/primer-nigerias-oilbunkering> (Retrieved 5 April, 2024)
- Daniel Balint-Kurti (2003). Nigerian anti-fraud tsar targets oil thieves. *Reuters*, November 12, 2003.
- Dornelles, B. (2016). The oil industry, illegal oil bunkering, and sustainable development in the Niger Delta. *Journal of Sustainable Development*, 9(1), 33-44.
- Ediri, E. (2022). *Scandalous oil theft: Nigeria loses 3.038 trillion in one year*. Retrieved from <https://www.vanguardngr.com/2022/05/scandalous-oil-theft-nigeria-loses-n3-038-trillion-in-one-year/>
- Effiong, E. (2019). Oil, armed violence, and marginalization in the Niger Delta. Stability. *International Journal of Security and Development*, 8(1), 1-14.
- Gilpin, R. (2018). *The political economy of international resources: Oil and national security*. Princeton University Press.
- Gubak, H. D. and Bulus, K. (2018). National security challenges and sustainable development in Nigeria: a critical analysis of the Niger Delta region. *Global Journal of Political Science and Administration*, 6(4), 32-50.
- Ibaba S. I. (2005). *Understanding the Niger Delta Crisis, Port Harcourt*. Jivac Publishing Company.
- Ikelegbe, A. (2005). The economy of conflict in the oil rich Niger Delta Region of Nigeria” *Nordic Journal of African Studies* 14(2), 208–234.

- Katsouris, C. & Sayne, A. (2013). *Nigeria's criminal crude: international Options to combat the Export of stolen oil*. Unpublished Report of the Royal Institute of International Affairs, Chatham House, London.
- Katsouris, C., & Sayne, A. (2013). *Nigeria's criminal crude: International options to combat the export of stolen oil*. London: Chatham House.
- Kenneth, M. (2021). *A wealth of sorrow: Why Nigeria's abundant oil reserves are really a curse*. <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2021/nov/09/a-wealth-of-sorrow-why-nigerias-abundant-oil-reserves-are-really-a-curse>.
- Mernyi, D. (2014). *Crude oil theft, pipeline vandalism cross over to 2014*. The Sun Newspapers, January, www.sunnewsonline.com
- Niger Delta Partnership Initiative (2022). *Illegal artisanal oil refining in the Niger Delta: Responding to environmental crime and insecurity*. Retrieved from <https://pindfoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Illegal-Artisanal-Oil-Refining-in-the-Niger-Delta-May-2022-Final.pdf>.
- Nkechi O. (2023). *Nigeria takes major step towards once again producing refined oil*. <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-67669181>.
- Obi, C. (2010). Oil Theft and Illegal Oil Refining in Nigeria: Implications for the Environment and Sustainable Development. *Global Majority E-Journal*, 1(2), 94-108.
- Okoh, J. (2018). The political economy of crude oil theft and illegal bunkering in Nigeria: A case study of the Niger Delta. *Journal of African Union Studies*, 7(1), 47-67.
- Raimi, L. (2023). Illegal oil bunkering in Nigeria's Niger Delta region: Prevalence and consequences. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Global Politics, Governance and Management*, 4(1), 203-218.
- Shrestha, R. (2017). Illegal oil bunkering and its socio-economic impact in the Caspian Sea Region. *Marine Policy*, 86, 191-197.
- Wilson, G. (2012) Militancy in the Niger Delta region and its impact on Nigerian State. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 2(1), 55-66.